

Transdisciplinarity and Three Mindsets for Sustainability in the Age of Cyber-physical Systems

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Abstract— Cyber-physical systems (CPS), such as collaborative robots, smart cities, and autonomous vehicles, are seen as decisive contributions to addressing many societal challenges. These systems have the power to provide solutions to cope with an aging population, address climate change, and improve issues of health, public safety and mobility. As a product of the fourth industrial revolution, these systems are currently inviting much interest. However, there are barriers that need to be considered and understood to be able to optimise the potential of these systems to support a more sustainable future. To this end, transdisciplinary skills and a combination of different mindsets are needed to be able to ask the right questions at the right time.

There are several approaches that can help us to initiate constructing innovative, transformative, future-oriented and systematic ideas and questions. The three important approaches that are suggested in this article are systems mindset, design mindset and futuristic mindset. These mindsets combined with the transdisciplinary perspective – where different disciplines work jointly to create sustainable solutions not only for today but also for tomorrow – have the power to change the world. This article underlines the importance of transdisciplinarity, presents the three mindsets and illustrates a hypothetical use case on how to blend these three mindsets to enable creative work in the future's transdisciplinary world for human-centred and sustainable future.

Index Terms— cyber-physical system, design thinking, future studies, sustainability, systems thinking.

I. INTRODUCTION

CYBER- physical systems are seen as the products of the fourth industrial revolution. They are an integration of computation, networking, and physical processes with feedback loops where physical processes affect computations and vice versa [1]. This gives them edge to not only operationalize the computation, automation and networking capabilities but also have the abilities to learn through the feedback loops and improve themselves over time. Collaborative robots, swarms of drones, smart cities and infrastructure, and autonomous vehicles are some examples of these types of systems.

When combined with the power of data, cyber-physical systems promise decisive contributions to societal challenges such as “coping with an aging population, addressing climate change, improving issues of health and public safety, supporting the transition to renewable energy resources, planning for megacities and tackling limited resources for better sustainability, equality, and mobility” [2]. It is not surprising that nearly every industry from manufacturing to healthcare, from construction to space exploration are working on understanding how to benefit from these systems.

While CPS are seen as promising systems to tackle societal and technical challenges, the success of them is very dependent on collaboration and integration of different disciplines. Moreover, this integration and collaboration is only possible when different stakeholders are able to understand each other and speak the same language. Several researchers have explored the leverage potential of new literacies for enhancing this necessity. For instance, Aoun [3] has identified three literacies that will help us to have the creative mindset and the mental elasticity to invent, discover, or create valuable solutions in the age of cyber-physical systems. These three new literacies are data literacy, technological literacy, and human literacy. He further explains that: the data literacy will help the workforce of the future to manage the flow of big data; technological literacy to know how the future systems work; and human literacy to deal with humanities, communication, and design – to function as a human being. Digital literacy is defined much earlier [4] as understanding and using information from various digital sources in various contexts for academic, career, and everyday life. Among others, Kirschenbaum [5] later detailed this further as digital humanities which is seen as an emergent field of study that integrates new forms of digital scholarship across different disciplines involving networks of people.

These different literacies can also be seen as an attempt to increase transdisciplinarity by extending one's

knowledge of emerging new areas. Similar to the development of mathematics being regarded as the fundamental knowledge underpinning engineering [6], development of computer literacy in the 1980s [7] or widespread understanding of the information literacy in the 1990s [8], the emergence of new programmes and curricula for enabling transdisciplinary skills development to foster technological, data and human literacies is expected.

This article aims to introduce, in addition to this transdisciplinary perspective, three important approaches: design mindset, futuristic mindset and systems mindset. These mindsets would play an important role to support transdisciplinary work of the current workforce and enable communities to ask the right questions at the right time. This ability – asking the right questions at the right time – will be a game changer in the age of cyber-physical systems. It will also initiate collaborations between disciplines working towards answering complex questions to achieve a sustainable and human-centred future. To this end, in the next section, the importance of transdisciplinarity for sustainable future is discussed. Then, in Section III the three mindsets are introduced and in Section IV an hypothetical example of using these mindsets in different development stages of a cyber-physical systems – smart city – is discussed. Lastly, the article concluded with Section V.

II. IMPORTANCE OF TRANSDISCIPLINARITY FOR SUSTAINABLE FUTURE

The concept of transdisciplinarity is defined as “a common system of axioms for a set of disciplines” [9] transcending the narrow scope of disciplinary worldviews through an overarching synthesis [10]. It deals with research problems that are defined from complex and heterogeneous domains [11], [12]. Max-Neef (2005) argues that “transdisciplinarity, more than a new discipline or super-discipline is, actually, a different manner of seeing the world, more systemic and more holistic.” (p. 15) While interdisciplinarity is important to construct common models or transfers tools between involved disciplines, transdisciplinarity “can go one step further in the science/society interface [14], [15] and instead focuses on articulations, preserving the different realities and confronting them in a controlled way.” (p. 33)

The 21st century is characterised by rapid change, uncertainty and increasing interconnectedness [16]. Moreover, the grand sustainability challenges of this century, including climate change, water scarcity, air pollution, forced migrations, poverty, deforestation, rising inequalities and more, are complex, encompass interdependent systems and pluralism of values within societies, and requires a holistic view. They simply cannot be adequately tackled from the sphere of specific individual disciplines [13] but require the consideration of perspectives through multiple lenses. Max-Neef [13] argues that as frequently attempted, creating interdisciplinary teams conformed of specialists in different areas, around a given problem, can only achieve an accumulation of visions emerging from participating disciplines. While this accumulation through interdisciplinarity can be beneficial for dealing with many technical problems, sustainability-related challenges necessitate an integrating synthesis, which cannot be achieved through an accumulation of visions. Yet today’s education mechanisms are still predominantly mono-disciplinary.

Tejedor et al. [15] suggest that “advancing sustainability science requires creating new long-term, participatory, solution-oriented programs as platforms to recognize and engage with the macro-ethical, adaptive and cross-disciplinary challenges embedded in professional issues.” (p. 29) This solution aims to transform the current research and development environments in due course. This, unfortunately, is not sufficient to deal with the challenges we are facing today. While the multidisciplinary groups are a must when working on sustainability research, additional supporting approaches are required in the meantime to initiate a creative, transformative, future-oriented way of thinking.

III. THREE MINDSETS

To deal with the complexity, heterogeneity and urgency of the sustainability-related challenges, we need to acquire new mindsets that can help individuals to support their thinking methods while fostering transdisciplinarity. In this article, the most promising three mindsets to explore are systems mindset, futuristic mindset and design mindset. While each one of these is effective to initiate new ideas, construct new perspectives or build long-term future scenarios and strategies, combining all three is a powerful way to deal with the uncertainty and complexity that sustainability problems often suffer from.

A. Systems Mindset

After being proposed by Ludwig Von Bertalanffy [17] as part of systems theory, systems thinking has been accepted, developed further and applied to different domains. Systems thinking is “a set of synergistic analytic

skills used to improve the capability of identifying and understanding systems, predicting their behaviours, and devising modifications to them in order to produce desired effects” [18]. In other words, systems thinking studies various elements within a system, their relationships to other activities within the system, looks for patterns over time and seeks root causes.

Systems mindset replaces reductionism – the belief that everything can be reduced to individual parts – with expansionism – the belief that a system is always a sub-system of some larger system – , and analysis – gaining knowledge of the system by understanding its parts – with synthesis – explaining its role in the larger system of which it is a part [19]. Additionally, it requires a shift from disconnections to interconnectedness, from linear to a circular way of thinking, from silos to emergence, from parts to wholes, and from isolation to relationships [20].

Interdependency and complexity demands systems thinking [21]–[25] and, as discussed before, sustainability challenges of today are nothing less than interdependent and complex.

B. Futuristic Mindset

The future studies are the systematic study of possible, probable and preferable futures including the worldviews from emerging technological and social changes. Futuristic mindset is the ability to use a set of tools to track, analyse, imagine, decide and act on these changes [26]. This is an important attitude to recognize opportunities before they evolve and to identify future user needs through revealing cognitive knowns and unknowns. The futuristic mindset can prepare individuals and organisations to study different perspectives of the future of phenomena years in advance.

Figure 1. Three main thinking models.

Originally, it was used for political, industrial, and economic forecasting [27]. Today, it has become obvious that future studies can also be applied to better understand any phenomenon including technology and innovation. Futuristic mindset uses scenario planning as a tool to carefully craft scenarios that could be important elements in the governance of innovation processes [28] and allows stakeholders to adopt tools for bringing foresight abilities into organisations [29]. These scenarios are considered to be a useful analytical tool for a better understanding of the change as well as the production and distribution of knowledge on change. This is extremely helpful for studying sustainability and for getting prepared for radical changes. Shifting the mindset from today to the future enables individuals and organisations to consider time and uncertainty when they strategize.

Since many of the today’s problems come from yesterday’s solutions, this long-term perspective has the potential to transform our future solutions. Futuristic mindset brings ability to look behind one’s own disciplinary boundaries, follow the changes in other domains, consider different outcomes of trends and uncertainties, imagine future scenarios and develop strategies for different futures. In a rapidly changing ambiguous world, without this way of thinking, it is impossible to achieve a sustainable future.

C. Design Mindset

Design thinking is "a human-centred approach to innovation that draws from the designer's toolkit to integrate the needs of people, the possibilities of technology, and the requirements for business success" [30]. Design mindset emphasizes observation, collaboration, fast learning, visualization of ideas, rapid concept prototyping, and concurrent business analysis, which ultimately influences innovation [31]. This attitude primarily concentrates on understanding the needs and experiences of the user (instead of hypothetical system requirements) as a source of inspiration and insight.

Design thinkers have proven to be more innovative because the design mindset is not problem-focused, it's solution-focused and action-oriented towards creating a preferred future. Thus, this approach is a subject of interest to many different domains. Design thinkers [32] empathize to understand people, within the context of the design challenge, define design elements to bring clarity and focus to the problem space, ideate without constraints and limitations, quickly prototype and solicit feedback from the users about the prototypes.

This process requires design thinkers to be open-minded, creative and innovative. The design mindset allows individuals to be playful, yet not get attached to their ideas. Sharing and listening through stories, storyboards, role-playing activities are very common when using a design toolkit [33]. This way of communicating through ambiguous or inherently subjective concepts such as emotions, needs, motivations, and drivers of behaviours, is extremely beneficial when discussing sustainability-related problems in multidisciplinary environments.

IV. DISCUSSION

The future cyber-physical systems will be autonomous, intelligent and connected. This connectivity, intelligence and autonomy has the potential to change the world and provide more sustainable future.

Figure 1 describes an illustrative framework on how the three mindsets could be used throughout the life cycle of CPS. In order to explain the importance and potential usage of this framework a short hypothetical case study is described and discussed in this section.

To illustrate how transdisciplinary teams can use the three mindsets, a smart cities concept has been selected. Smart cities can be defined as cities that use information and communication technologies to improve the functions and experiences in and around the cities. The concept of smart cities is discussed, evaluated and criticised by several scholars. This paper does not aim to include these due to the limitations and scope of this works. Instead, here we will only use a hypothetical smart city as an example to highlight potential usage of the transdisciplinary framework with three mindsets.

IEEE Standards Association [33] defines series of standards from smart grid, energy efficiency, intelligent transportation, learning technologies, smart homes, and eHealth to Internet of Things, eGovernance and cyber security. At the same time, IEEE Smart Cities [34] argues that smart cities bring together technology, government and society and includes smart economy, smart energy, smart mobility, smart environment, smart living, and smart governance. As these examples summarise, it is impossible for a cyber-physical system, such as a smart city, to be understood, designed or developed by one team belonging to one discipline. To develop any service or product for smart cities, teams need to understand different systems, levels, interactions, interconnections and think about key performance indicators, as well as functional and non-functional specifications. The activities and tools from systems thinking – design thinking and future studies – should be applied by domain experts, users, and citizens in transdisciplinary teams to improve the success of the end products and to secure sustainable and human-centred outcomes.

In this example use case, five stages are proposed as part of the development cycle, including: ideate; design; build; operate; and integrate. These stages, and a brief explanation of how different mindsets and tools from these may be used, are defined below.

Ideate: Ideally, any development efforts for cyber-physical systems should start with the ideation process. At this stage, the futuristic mindset would guide the transdisciplinary groups to identify future trends, drivers and uncertainties. Being aware of these important factors would be helpful to understand how the world may look like in the future and support the team(s) to focus on this horizon by considering changes not only in a smart cities context, but also in a technological, social, political, economical context which directly affects the smart cities. At the same time, the design mindset could enable the team(s) to implement workshops, in order to build rough prototypes to empathise, test and collect feedback from the users – in this case citizens of the city. While the futuristic mindset helps to see the interrelationships between different contextual worlds, systems thinking could provide information to understand how the ideated new product, service or development would fit in relation to the bigger picture.

Design: After the ideation process where the future changes in the contextual worlds around the smart cities are discussed and analysed, several prototypes are shared with the citizens whose expectations, experiences and suggestions are collected. At this stage teams can start to work on designing new solutions or products. During the design phase, teams(s) should consider providing environments and opportunities for users to give feedback and to test new ideas on the design and functionalities of the product/solution. While continuously testing the more sophisticated prototypes, it is important not to lose the future and systems perspectives. The possibilities of how the new solution/product/functionality/design may work with other solutions/products/functionality/designs should be discussed and communicated in transdisciplinary teams.

Build: One of the most crucial stages of new implementations is the building phase of the solution/product/functionality/design. While the users' feedback and expectations are captured earlier than this stage, it is important to secure definition of functional and non-functional requirements related to the development. Systems thinking is very important at this stage because there is a risk that the actual development could only focus to fulfil these simplified requirements and the resulting simplifications would reflect a different level of expectations. For that reason, the transdisciplinary teams should always include members from different phases of the development cycle and perform reality check at different stages. This balance between designing for experiences and building with existing tools is challenging, but in the long run delivers a much more rewarding experience for the teams. Moreover, ethical, social and moral discussions on how to develop sustainable solutions would benefit the teams and potentially facilitate them to evolve and acquire new thinking models.

Operate: As discussed briefly, today, we expect CPS to be intelligent and act autonomously during the operations. At this stage, the systems mindset can support the teams to acknowledge the connections, relationships, patterns and mental models, and help support analysis and evaluations of the end result. A design mindset will validate if the provided solution is really performing the way it is expected, collect insights and feedbacks from the citizens, while starting to identify ways to innovate further functionalities and improvements.

Integrate: The overall benefits of cyber-physical systems – providing solutions to sustainability challenges to cope with an aging population, address climate change, and improve issues of health, public safety and mobility – emerge from the integration of different systems. This integration is not only important for interoperability issues of the operations, but also further data collection, analysis and decision-making mechanisms. At this stage, all three mindsets need to be considered again because integration is not only about connecting two systems, but connecting them for a purpose. Some important questions include: which systems to integrate; what solutions and tools should be used for better interoperability; how the integrated systems will affect sustainability; and are there any risks for unintended consequences or unexpected rebound effects. It is necessary to observe the changes in the contextual world, identify the trends and uncertainties. Additionally, understanding the impact of change, and imagining alternative futures would help decision-making on integration. Similarly, it is beneficial to discuss these changes with the end users and try to understand the new experiences which may follow as a result of these changes, to look for any patterns, and to re-evaluate the whole system through the perspective of sustainability.

V. CONCLUSION

There is no reason to believe that the rapidly changing, interconnected world of today will become more simple or slower. Cyber-physical systems will continue to rise in forms of collaborative robots, digitalised infrastructure, autonomous vehicles, and smart cities. Yet, we will continue to deal with increased complexity and ambiguity. Right now, the immediate challenge is Covid-19, yesterday it was floods, tsunamis, earthquakes; before that it was economic crises and wars. It is impossible to predict when and what will happen, yet we know that these uncertain, unexpected complex events will happen. The only way to solve the challenges in all three dimensions of sustainable development – economic, social and environmental – is to invite a shift in our mindset. This shift can be achieved over time through transdisciplinarity programmes.

We should educate the engineers, developers, workers, managers, and scientists of the future to become more transdisciplinary. This is a long-term solution. At the same time, we need to employ different mindsets and allow different thinking models to flourish. The three mindsets that we have discussed – systems mindset, design mindset and futuristic mindset – are important tools to put to use right away. Systems thinking is required because today's world is interconnected, and everything has the potential to affect everything else. We should move from disconnections to interconnections, from linear thinking to circular thinking, from silos to emergence, from parts to wholes, from analysis to synthesis. Design thinking is needed because we should design for people with people. While some organisations will always work on providing solutions, some of us should work on understanding the needs and problems without being limited to technologies. And futuristic thinking is essential to deal with the unknown unknowns, to provide solutions not just for the world we live in today but also for tomorrow – and to

be prepared for the unexpected.

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